

Deporting Logic

Why the Rwanda Asylum Plan's Lack of Ethics, Legality, Logic, & Long-Term Economic Decision Making will ultimately Doom the Policy

The United Kingdom and the Republic of Rwanda: two countries, a world apart. The United Kingdom, one of the planet's wealthiest Global North nations, whose wealth and power was accumulated through a complicated past of brutal colonization, recently agreed to a landmark referendum: Brexit. In the meantime, the Global South nation of Rwanda continues the arduous process of rebranding its international image after one of the worst humanitarian crises to ever occur: the Rwandan Genocide. Whereas the UK is a country looking inward and concentrating on its own national interests, Rwanda is an ambitious country looking outward for new economic opportunities (Latif Dahir, 2022). In 2022, the two nations – an unlikely pairing at that – agreed to what is now known as the 'Rwanda Asylum Plan' (BBC, October 2022). This agreement will have the UK pay Rwanda for its services in taking on the large number of refugees who have recently embarked in Britain (Latif Dahir, 2022). While at first glance this negotiation may seem to assist both nations, beneath the media-friendly smiles and photos at the negotiation table lies poor economic decision making and unethical treatment of migrants likely to doom this policy. In short, *The Rwanda Asylum Plan is a fundamentally bad policy because of the human rights abuses in Rwanda, the reversal of critical human refugee and migration standards, and the overall poor economic planning of the policy.* Before beginning to analyze the

root of the policy's problems, it is first essential to further understand the context leading up to this policy, and the official agreements on the part of both nations.

The landlocked Republic of Rwanda is one of Africa's smallest and most densely populated nations (Latif Dahir, 2022). The country borders Burundi to the south, Tanzania to the east, Uganda to the northeast, and the Democratic Republic of the Congo to the west and northwest. At the helm of Rwanda's governmental leadership is President Paul Kagame, who has been president since the year 2000, though has informally been considered the country's leader since 1994. At that time, the Rwandan Genocide had amassed a million fatalities in a little over three months (Latif Dahir, 2022). During the Rwandan Genocide, Kagame had been General of the Rwandan Patriotic Front – known as the RPF for short – which was the movement opposing the Hutu tribe's genocide of the minority Tutsi tribe (Waldorf, 2017, pp. 71-72). When Kagame and the RPF defeated the genocidal forces opposing them, any and all structural institutions that might have obstructed his ascent to absolute political power had been decimated; Kagame had, “...the moral authority, political power and military means to refashion Rwanda.” (Waldorf, 2017, p. 72).

Though under authoritarian rule – more on this later – Kagame's Rwanda has seen a strong economic resurgence (Waldorf, 2017, p. 73). Rwanda has developed its subsistence agriculture into a larger agribusiness, established an information technology industry, and has attracted corporations from abroad in parts due to its low corporate tax rates (Waldorf, 2017, p. 73). While Rwanda's annual growth rate and GDP have risen, the nation has also met some 21st Century standards on maternal health and primary education (Waldorf, 2017, p. 73). As written by journalist Abdi Latif Dahir, President Kagame “...has transformed the nation into an

ambitious state that punches above its weight politically, economically and on the security front.” (Latif Dahir, 2022). One of the many tactics President Kagame is employing to turn the international spotlight onto Rwanda is its recent embrace of refugees from many fellow Global South countries. Refugees migrating from other African countries, such as Burundi, Eritrea, and Somalia are currently being housed by Rwanda – as seen in Image 1 of the list of Figures – in addition to Middle East nations like Afghanistan (Latif Dahir, 2022). President Kagame has stated that, “...his government is motivated by altruism and a moral responsibility to provide a solution to “a very complicated problem all over the world.” ” (Latif Dahir, 2022). At a glance, the rather encouraging steps Rwanda has taken as a nation to kickstart its economy and embrace mass amounts of refugees seemingly support this claim with flying colors.

Meanwhile, approximately 4,000 miles to the northwest (BBC, October 2022) – as seen in Image 2 of the List of Figures – lies the United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland. The United Kingdom contains four countries: England, Wales, Scotland, and Northern Ireland. The UK only shares a land border with Ireland, though maritime borders include the Irish Seas between Ireland and Great Britain, the North Sea to the east of Great Britain, the Atlantic Ocean to the northwest, and the English Channel to the south towards mainland Europe. These last six years in the UK have undoubtedly represented a great change in the nation’s foreign and domestic policy, largely stemming from the 2016 Referendum Vote on ‘Brexit’. This decision, in which the UK just narrowly voted to enact, called for the withdrawal of the United Kingdom from the European Union upon the year 2020. According to polls, a whole third of people who voted to leave the European Union cited their main reason as immigration reform, such that the UK could, “...regain control over immigration and its own borders.” (Ashcroft,

2016). On the other hand, UK voters who positively perceived globalization, multiculturalism, and immigration voted overwhelmingly to remain in the European Union (Ashcroft, 2016). Since the referendum voted in favor of leaving, there has been a massive influx of migrants crossing the English Channel from continental Europe into England and the United Kingdom as a whole. It is important to note here the influence of the UK's geography, as unlike some Mediterranean nations – primarily Spain, Italy, and Greece – the UK is not used to receiving the 'blunt' of the EU's refugee demand from Northern African and Middle Eastern nations. With nearly 30,000 migrants crossing the English Channel in just a year though (BBC, October 2022) – as seen by Image 3 of the List of Figures – many British citizens are concerned (BBC, April 2022). Polls prior to the launch of the new Rwanda Asylum Plan suggested that about 60% of citizens were unhappy with the government's migration policies, with a majority expressing concern specifically over Channel crossings (BBC, April 2022). A few months ago, then UK Prime Minister Boris Johnson expressed his concern of migrants crossing the English Channel, saying that, "...action was needed to stop "vile people smugglers" turning the ocean into a "watery graveyard....". (BBC, April 2022). For many desperate refugees, smuggling themselves over the English Channel in small boats – as seen by the two main routes in Image 4 of the List of Figures – is the well-known way to get to the UK (Wallis, 2020). All of these concerns come at a time in history in which many Western and Global North nations are establishing stricter migration and border policies (Latif Dahir, 2022). Looking to relieve itself of the constant influx of migrants, some of which undocumented, the suddenly ambitious Rwanda presented the UK with an opportunity to take their refugee problem right off their hand. It just came with a hefty price tag.

The official guidelines of the deal are as follows: the UK will screen asylum seekers once embarking upon British shores, and will then send the personal information of such asylum seekers to Rwanda's government (Terry, 2022). Rwanda then has the right to select which of the asylum seekers it so chooses, and for those migrants that they do not select, the UK will deport them elsewhere. For those that are selected to go to Rwanda, the United Kingdom's government flies these migrants out to Rwanda, where they are given housing also paid for by the UK (Terry, 2022). This policy will be given an initial trial run of five years (BBC, October 2022).

The first of many fundamental problems that arises from this policy decision are the ethical concerns of the treatment of refugees in Rwanda. The most indicting impression on a country's human rights track record – or lack thereof – is that country's ruler and government. While Rwanda claims to have fair elections, the reality is that President Kagame masks his authoritarian government behind the veil of these so-called 'elections'. Such evidence is seen in the imprisonment of Kagame's political opponents and independent journalists, the prevention of opposing political parties from getting on voting ballots, and the government's continuous refusal of election oversight by human rights groups (Waldorf, 2017, p. 83). More extreme than this however has been the assassinations of certain, opposing political figures, largely believed to be requested by Kagame. In the past, high-profile opponents of Kagame have been shot, beheaded, and have even 'disappeared' altogether (Waldorf, 2017, p. 83). There is notable evidence that the UK knew of such authoritarianism and only recently overlooked it in favor of the new partnership with Kagame's government. 16 months before the deal was made, in January 2021, Boris Johnson said that Rwanda, "...restricts civil and political rights and media freedom..."; once the partnership was announced in April 2022, Johnson said that Rwanda was,

“....one of the safest countries in the world, globally recognized for its record of welcoming and integrating migrants....” (Terry, 2022). This sudden, hypocritical reversal on Rwanda’s human rights heavily implicates the UK, exhibiting an egregious desire to value the new negotiation over doing what may be right. It should also be noted that during the Rwandan Genocide, Kagame displayed a shocking indifference to the death of migrants in his own country, stating, “If the [Tutsi] refugees have to be killed for the cause, they will be considered as part of the sacrifice.” (Waldorf, 2017, p. 72). Kagame’s comments and the RPF’s subsequent opposition of UN peacekeeping efforts to rescue Tutsi lives shows just how far Kagame and his followers are willing to go to prioritize certain objectives over the wellbeing of even the people he was supposedly fighting to protect (Waldorf, 2017, p. 72). While one could counter-argue that with war comes difficult decisions, what is the argument for the present-day treatment of refugees in Rwanda? The country’s supposed ‘altruism’ towards migrants is apparently immune to the imprisonment and expulsion of such refugees, along with the prejudicial denial of asylum to L.G.B.T.Q. refugees (Latif Dahir, 2022). Under Kagame, the Rwandan government has been known to recruit refugees in order to, “....conduct armed operations in neighboring countries....” (Latif Dahir, 2022). When refugees protested an government-issued cut in food rations a few years back, Rwandan police shot and killed 12 protesters; one man who was accused of his involvement in the protest tried to flee to Kenya before being kidnapped and tortured by Rwandan authorities (Latif Dahir, 2022). In fact, torture is supposedly ordinary for many asylum seekers says Human Rights Watch Director Lewis Mudge, who stated that, “....arbitrary detention, ill-treatment, and torture in facilities is commonplace.” (Terry, 2022). Beyond the threat of torture though is the concern over Rwanda’s lack of land resources. Frank Habienza,

one of Kagame's more high-profile political opponents, has said that the deal is unsustainable due to the existing competition for land resources amongst even permanent Rwandan citizens (Terry, 2022). A prime example of this is what occurred at the Hope Hostel in the Rwandan capital of Kigali just this past August. Though the UK's deported refugees have yet to arrive, the Rwandan government has forced residents of the Hope Hostel to leave the building permanently in order to provide housing for the new refugees (Syal, 2022). The Hope Hostel, originally built to house endangered survivors of the Rwandan genocide, has since housed underprivileged students whose families were murdered in the genocide. Although the hostel is still empty and awaiting upon the legal clearance – more on that later – of the UK's migrants, some of these residents have now been homeless and living in poverty (Syal, 2022). Ultimately, there is no logic in taking on another country's refugees and asylum seekers if it means that nation must endanger its most disadvantaged students of the next generation. Rwanda is a great example of why a policy such as the Rwanda Asylum Plan lies on shaky ground. Though the country has undoubtedly made important strides domestically over the last 28 years, there are still many more systemic issues to be addressed internally before the country should look to become a central solution to the world's refugee crisis. This is not to say that Rwanda should not accept refugees, just not those who did not consent to be exported there – more on this in a moment – through international dealings. With a frightening lack of civil freedoms, a tendency for torture and military recruitment, and a lack of existing resources for both current citizens and refugees, Rwanda should not be making deals to take on deported refugees. What is arguably worse however is the UK's knowledge of Rwanda's authoritarian government and history with

refugees. If the deal finally passes through court, the UK would also be responsible for potential Human Rights Abuses in Rwanda, as much as they may choose to turn a 'blind eye' to it.

The second, main fundamental flaw with the Rwanda Asylum Plan is its illogic and illegality regarding migration policy. In 1951, the *Convention Relating to the Status of Refugees* defines a refugee as, "Any person who owing to well-founded fear of being persecuted for reasons of race, religion, nationality, membership of particular social group or political opinion, is outside the country of his nationality and is unable, or owing to such fear, unwilling to avail himself of the protection of that country." (Orchard, 2014, pp. 1-2). Refugees are the world's most disadvantaged people, and are oftentimes just in search of safety, employment, and support. Part of the 1951 Referendum includes the assurance that asylum seekers will not be returned to a country where their freedoms are threatened, which in this case includes Rwanda (Terry, 2022). In the context of this globally agreed-upon definition, the Rwanda Asylum Plan therefore reverses the standards regarding refugee protections. The United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees has come out and admonished the policy, stating that the UK has ".....an obligation to ensure access for asylum seekers – integrating those deemed to be refugees and safely returning to their country of origin, people with no legal basis to stay." (UN News, 2022). Even before the 1951 Refugee Convention, the UK made assurances to uphold international norms and protect political refugees (Orchard, 2014, p. 222). Nevertheless, the UK has gone ahead and has been taking steps to defer the responsibility of their refugees elsewhere, endangering the sanctity of the international refugee protection regime (UN News, 2022). Fortunately, the European Court of Human Rights has intervened and even grounded the first migrant-filled planes from leaving for Rwanda; the legal fight will now likely extend for months in European Court, ironically proving

that the UK still only has so much independence from the rest of Europe (Lee & Faulkner, 2022). Even after putting aside the illegality of this particular policy though, this plan will still likely backfire policy-wise for both nations considering the state of refugees in the 21st century. First, it is important to debunk the supposed thought that developed nations are home to the largest numbers of refugees. This is false, and in fact, about 85% of refugees globally are currently living in developing nations (Terry, 2022). If the fundamental idea of this policy is to relieve developed nations of the burden of asylum seekers, then the logic is wrong on behalf of the UK. Instead, this will only theoretically exacerbate the world's current refugee crisis by placing more and more people in need into a country that cannot properly provide for them. This will then cause even more people to emigrate from a developing country such as Rwanda in search of a developed nation with proper resources, like the United Kingdom. Also, if the UK believes this policy will motivate refugees to stop making the journey across the English Channel, they are still wrong. People find a way, especially those that have already sacrificed so much to make it all the way across continental Europe to reach the English Channel. More importantly however, stricter enforcements of border policies have been shown to fail in the past. A study by the American Journal of Sociology proved that a heightened enforcement of border policy in America in the 1980s has in part helped exacerbate America's current immigration and refugee crisis – as seen in Images 5a and 5b in the List of Figures (Massey et al. 2016). After all, border policies do not address the root causes of migration, such as the mitigation of foreign crises or the higher wages and labor demand in developed nations. It also does not factor in already existing countermeasures and networks of border enforcement. While the US has continued to spend more and more on immigration policies, migrants have simultaneously continued to

evolve their means of crossing the border; this proves that stricter enforcement of borders at common, legal entry points will simply cause more entries of refugees from less supervised, illegal entry points. Finally, the US' stricter border policies have made it more difficult – and has thus stopped trends of – transnational migration between the US and other Central American countries; now, migrants are making more permanent settlements in America (Massey et al. 2016). In a similar manner, the UK must understand that in the current geopolitical climate, this policy will not deter migrants like the government says it will (BBC, October 2022). Instead, it will likely increase the propensity of refugees to be smuggled illegally, as well as potentially discouraging migrants from eventually returning to their homes – if they can. The United Kingdom's government is already witnessing just how much of a legal nightmare this policy is, while seeming completely oblivious to the many flaws of logic this policy would have – if it finally goes through – and how it could only amplify the current increase in refugee crossings. In the meantime, Rwanda could very well tarnish its own national rebranding efforts on a bigger, global stage if the policy magnifies the African nation's existing lack of resources and economic development. This includes the ethical reasons cited before, and the economic concerns of the African country's new agreement.

The final fundamental problem with this policy is its poor economic decision making on the part of both countries; while the UK is prioritizing a short-term pay-out over long-term economic growth, Rwanda is potentially catapulting themselves into an employment crisis with this deal. As agreed to in the initial negotiations of this deal, the UK will – if it has not already – pay an upfront cost of 120 million Euros to Rwanda (BBC, October 2022). The chartering of planes with necessary services would likely cost about 13,000 Euros per person, and the program

as a whole would cost the UK a staggering 1.5 billion Euros annually. Much of the fiscal concerns for the UK's policy lies in the daily cost of detaining refugees in the UK while Rwanda selects who it wants to be deported (BBC, October 2022). Instead of providing these migrants the means to meaningfully contribute to the workforce, the UK is instead willing to go through painstaking efforts to vet as many migrants as it can. Migrants are held in holding centers for over a year on average, centers that can cost taxpayers £150 a day, only for more than 70% of detainees to be told that they can stay in the UK after all (Jenkins, 2022). The economic argument here on behalf of Boris Johnson and the Conservative Party of the UK though is that by exporting refugees to Rwanda, the UK will conserve money. Studies have proven this claim to be false however. The University of Oxford explained that the fiscal impact of migrants in the UK is minute, just a mere 1% of the nation's gross domestic product (Vargas-Silva et al. 2022). Furthermore, the study went on to explain that education is the largest expense of refugees is education (Vargas-Silva et al. 2022), something that the UK should not be too concerned about since the majority of recent refugees are single men from Iran (Terry, 2022). This same study also determined that the most recent wave of refugees consistently have a more positive impact fiscally than their predecessors, an advantage the UK is openly turning away (Vargas-Silva et al. 2022). The only policy in recent history that is even remotely similar to the Rwanda Asylum Plan is that of the agreement between Australia and nations Nauru (Gallardo, 2022). While of course different, this similar system in deporting refugees offshore cost the Australian taxpayer an average of 1.7 million Euros (Gallardo, 2022), and is now highly disapproved of back in Australia (Amin & Kwai, 2018). Even if the Rwanda Asylum Plan is approved in international court, this policy will continue to seemingly cause the UK to bleed money in order to uphold its

detention camps. As for Rwanda, despite the provided accommodations of housing, very few economic opportunities are available to refugees who live isolated from such jobs in refugee camps (UN News, 2022). Through recent interviews, current refugees in Rwanda cited their boredom and lack of employment, with one refugee claiming that a lack of work leads to a lack of food (Ssuuna, 2022). It begs the question: why would Rwanda go through all this trouble to bring migrants and aspiring workers to Rwanda if the nation was just going to provide for their housing and limit their economic opportunities? From a certain point of view, it would seem Rwanda is going through a great deal of trouble to provide resources for these refugees, only to not allow these people to then invest back in the nation.

Human Rights abuses in Rwanda, legal difficulties in international court, logical fallacies regarding migration, a prioritization of short-term economics if that: the Rwanda Asylum Plan is an inherently bad policy. At the end of the day, poor decision making is the central theme of the Rwanda Asylum Plan, and bad policies and misguided politicians come and go. What does not merely 'come and go' though is xenophobia. It was announced recently that the UK's new Home Secretary, Suella Braverman, is now hoping to expand the policy of deporting migrants before it has even officially begun (Jenkins, 2022). Rather than exclusively sending migrants to Rwanda, Secretary Braverman hopes to offshore refugees to other developing nations such as Belize, Peru, and Paraguay (Jenkins, 2022). While it is still to be seen whether or not the current plan with Rwanda will even go through in international court, there is a growing interest in this policy's framework as a 'solution' for Global North nations. Denmark, a country within the European Union, has expressed interest in negotiating a similar deal with Rwanda (Terry, 2022). Though one could argue that the UK's post-Brexit government has influenced these decisions, the

question remains on whether or not this could trickle down to European Union countries as well. If it does, and more countries follow suit, international protections for refugees could continue to deteriorate, and developed nations may begin to view developing nations as a means to dispose of their own geopolitical burdens. The African Union themselves has largely expressed concerns over the deportation of refugees to Africa and other developing nations, claiming that these policies are examples of xenophobia and modern European neocolonialism (Terry, 2022). It is essential that this philosophy is extinguished before it can take root, otherwise misinformation and xenophobia may become the leading values of 21st century migration policies. To prevent this, what needs to be understood first is that the increase in global refugee numbers over the past few decades is influenced by the increased duration of civil wars and conflicts from which refugees are fleeing (Orchard, 2014, p. 203). This new wave of refugees over the last 30 plus years has also not fit the mold of post-WWII refugees, most of whom were seen as white, anti-communist males; now, xenophobic messaging has influenced many to view modern-day asylum seekers as mass abusers of hospitality (Orchard, 2014, p. 205). In fact, many Western World and Global North nations echoed sentiments of support for refugees from Communist states not so much as to support the refugees, but to, “....further reinforce internal political support for an anti-Soviet, anti-communist foreign policy because Western generosity would reinforce the domestic constituencies' indignation at the evils of communist ideology and oppression.” (Keely, 2001, p. 308). Flash forward to present day, and in 2016, the United Kingdom received the majority of its migrants from Iran, Eritrea, Afghanistan and Syria (Noja et al. 2018), all countries hailing from East Africa and the Middle East. These are not white people indirectly helping to perpetuate anti-communist rhetoric; these are non-white people of need fleeing states of turmoil. The 1951

Refugee Convention forbids policy-making based on discrimination, but it is now in which mainly Iranian refugees are being viewed as security threats (Terry, 2022). While the UK is to a degree more independent now due to Brexit, it is imperative that the European Union assures that its nations provide refugee protections established by the 1951 Convention, and that it provides the necessary labor, health, and liberty rights (Frelick et al. 2016).

The Rwanda Asylum Plan displays just how important geography, especially the intersection of Global North and Global South nations are, in dictating the future of the world's migration policies: whether for good, or worse.

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List of Figures

Image 1: Existing Refugee Camps in Rwanda

Source: (Operational Data Portal – UNHCR, 2018)

Image 2: Map Portraying Distance Between United Kingdom & Rwanda

Source: (BBC, October 2022)

Image 3: Tracking English Channel Migrants (1/1/2019 - 4/12/2022)

Source: (BBC, April 2022)

People crossing the English Channel in boats

Source: BBC research/Home Office, latest data to 12 Apr **BBC**

Image 4: Two Main Refugee Routes Over the English Channel

Source: (Wallis, 2020)

Image 5a: America’s Border Patrol Budget on Migration Policies from 1970 - 2013

Source: (Massey et al. 2016)

Image 5b: Observed and Predicted Cost in Border Smuggling over US-Mexico

Border from 1970 - 2010

Source: (Massey et al. 2016)

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